

Women Empowerment: Contribution of Raja Rammohan Roy

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Dr.A.S.Mallika

*Associate Professor and Head, Department of Political Science
JBAS College for Women, Chennai*

Women all over the world remain a widely oppressed section. The principle patriarchy accentuates male domination and female subordination. Women constitute slightly more than half of the world population. Their contribution to the social and economic development of societies is also more than half as compared to that of men by virtue of their dual roles in the productive and reproductive spheres. Yet, their participation in formal political structures and processes, where decisions regarding the use of societal resources generated by both men and women are made, remains insignificant. Presently, women's representation in legislatures around the world is 15 per cent. Despite the pronounced commitment of the international community to gender equality and bridging the gender gap in the formal political arena, reinforced by the Convention on Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) and the Beijing Platform of Action, there are only twelve countries where women hold 33 per cent or more seats in the Parliament (UNDP Report, 2005).

Equality and empowerment of women are necessary to bring about an egalitarian human society. Societies cannot succeed by suppressing the talents of half of their members. Promoting gender equality and empowerment of women was declared as an important millennium development goal adopted by the Millennium Summit held in New York in Sept., 2000.

Women in India constitute a great mass of illiterate and powerless humanity. In the Post Independence era women were chiefly seen as recipients of benefit and welfare measures. But in the post 1970s they began to be seen as agents of development. However, the development process was often intertwined with complex forms of discrimination, exploitation and violence hampering the progress of women. Rising incidence of female foeticide, dowry deaths, custodian and gang rape is a mere preview into the much deeper oppressive conditions of women that fail to get addressed emphatically.

The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. The Constitution not only grants

equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women. Within the framework of a democratic polity, our laws, development policies, Plans and programmes have aimed at women's advancement in different spheres. From the Fifty Five Year Plan (1974-78) onwards has been a marked shift in the approach to women's issues from welfare to development. In recent years, the empowerment of women has been recognized as the central issue in determining the status of women. The National Commission for Women was set up by an Act of Parliament in 1990 to safeguard the rights and legal entitlements of women. The 73rd and 74th Amendments (1993) to the Constitution of India have provided for reservation of seats in the local bodies of Panchayats and Municipalities for women, laying a strong foundation for their participation in decision making at the local levels. India has also ratified various international conventions and human rights instruments committing to secure equal rights of women. Key among them is the ratification of the Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) in 1993.

The Mexico Plan of Action (1975), The Nairobi Forward Looking Strategies (1985), the Beijing Declaration as well as the Platform for Action (1995) and the Outcome Document adopted by the UNGA Session on Gender Equality and Development & Peace for the 21st century, titled "Further actions and initiatives to implement the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action" has been unreservedly endorsed by India for appropriate follow up. The Policy also takes note of the commitments of the Ninth Five Year Plan and the other Sectoral Policies relating to empowerment of Women. The women's movement and a wide-spread network of non-Government Organisations which have strong grass-roots presence and deep insight into women's concerns have contributed in inspiring initiatives for the empowerment of women.

However, there still exists a wide gap between the goals enunciated in the Constitution, legislation, policies, plans, programmes, and related mechanisms on the one hand and the situational reality of the status of women in India, on the other. This has been analysed extensively in the Report of the Committee on the Status of Women in India. "Towards Equality", 1974 and highlighted in the National Perspective Plan for Women, 1988-2000, the Shramshakti Report, 1988 and the Platform for Action, Five Years After – An Assessment" Gender disparity manifests itself in various forms, the most obvious being the trend of continuously declining female ratio in the population in the last few decades. Social stereotyping and violence at the domestic and societal levels are some of the other manifestations. Discrimination against girl children, adolescent girls and women persists in parts of the country. The underlying causes of gender inequality are related to social and economic structure, which is based on informal and formal norms, and practices. Consequently, the access of women particularly those belonging to weaker sections including Scheduled Casts /Scheduled Tribes/ Other backward Classes and minorities, majority of whom are in the rural areas and in the informal, unorganized sector – to education, health and productive resources, among others, is inadequate. Therefore, they remain largely marginalized, poor and socially excluded.

Empowerment is a multidimensional process and refers to the expansion of freedom of choice and action in all spheres – social, political, cultural and economic. It implies control over resources and autonomy in decision making. At the individual level it refers to enhancing individual capabilities and at the collective level, it stands for the ability to organize and mobilize, to take action and, to solve their problems. Empowerment urgently calls for effective enforcement of constitutional rights of women, and social legislations, repeal of discriminatory laws, gender sensitization of the law enforcing machinery, capacity building and attitudinal change through education, restructuring of unequal social, economic and political relations, increasing access to education, health care, nutrition and employment.

The process of empowerment of women in third world countries like India is proceeding at a pace which falls below expectations. Women's rights and status are India in a vulnerable stage since the early Rig-Vedic periods till now. Women in India are still facing major obstacles in performing their duties, implementing their thoughts and victimized by male dominating attitudes. So, empowerment in its truest sense is not feasible as the problem is rooted at a deeper level. Reservation for women is not sufficient to solve the problem and the need to awaken the consciousness of the masses towards gender equality and redressal of the social biases towards women are of utmost importance and urgency. It is true that women in India are enjoying their freedom of speech and expressions and actions in a better way than before yet it has been possible only through the ignition of awareness among the masses and enlightenment through education is playing a major role behind it.

In India, women's status and position have changed periodically in a vacillating manner. There were lot of efforts made by many great social reformers and intellectuals in uplifting women's position in society. Raja Rammohan Roy, The Father of modern India, is one of the most prominent figures among them. He is widely praised for his outstanding contribution to socio-religious-cultural-economic and political fields of the Indian society. His enormous exertion to uplift women in all spheres of society is one of the salient features of his progressive agenda which placed him at the apex of great honours.

The women community was always portrayed as subordinate to their male counterparts from the end of Vedic period and the lives of women were taken as granted to serve the male section of society. Raja Rammohan Roy visualized the miserable condition of women in all aspects of society and vehemently stood against all kinds of animosity against them. He welcomed and supported all progressive effects and elements to rescue the women community from the existing discriminating and depriving factors. He gave his support to the British government in its progressive reforms and initiatives, formed social organizations and propagated women liberation thoughts through the press and mass media. Roy advocated in favour of introduction of modern scientific education among Indians and emphasized on the role of civil society. He wanted to extricate the masses from all kinds of degradation by encouraging them to exercise their faculties of logical thinking and reasoning.

Raja Rammohan Roy wrote innumerable articles, letters and distributed them free of cost to build public opinion against the barbarous practice of Sati to eradicate it from the grassroots of Hindu society. He wanted to supplant obscurantism with rationalism in the human mind. In his three works – 'Sahamara Bisiya Prabartak O nibartak Sambad' (1818), 'Sahamara Bisoye Prabartak O Nibartak Dwitiyo Sambad' (1819 and 'Sahamara Bisoye (1820) he gave the proper interpretation of ancient Hindu religious scriptures and declared the practice of Sati had no scriptural sanction. In his another article 'Brief Remarks Regarding Modern Encroachment on the Ancient Right of Female' (1822) Roy stood for the property rights of women and illustrated how women should get their share as men in their families.

Raja Rammohan Roy launched two newspapers 'Sambad Kaumudi' (1821) in Bengali and 'Mirat-U1-Akbar' (1822) in Persian to propagate his socio-religious views as he was aware that the mass media was one of the platforms of communication easier to reach out the people's mind. In 1817 Roy wrote an article in Sambad Kaumudi, titled 'Abolition of Sati', Kaumudi frequently published its articles regarding the miserable condition of women in their family life and society. In editorials of Mirat-U1 Ukbar Roy wrote in favour of women rights of inheritance and argued for equal sharing of property between month and son. Roy also expressed his political and religious views in the column of Mirant-U1-Abar. Thus the ideas of women's liberation were often published in these two newspapers and people were requested to share their undesirable daily social experiences with the media.

Raja Rammohan Roy did not get the proper support from his countrymen in favour of his progressive activities. But he felt the importance of the inevitable role of civil society in the awakening the consciousness of the masses towards gender-equality. His advanced thinking inspired a group of young people. The members of 'Young Bengal' also had a deep regard to his progressive ideas. He preached the futility of the celebration of cremation of widow women with her husband's pyre through his followers also. He also took initiatives to make a fund with the help of wealthy people of Bengal to provide subsistence to these widows. He wanted to provide subsistence to these widows. He wanted to create a new society based on tolerance, reasoning, and humanity and took initiatives to lead the people in the path of national solidarity to ensure national independence from colonial rule. For this major purpose he felt the necessity of existence of a strong civil society.

Conclusion

Raja Rammohan Roy visualized the need of scientific, rational and progressive education for the India. For this purpose he took initiatives to awaken the conscience of the masses through the civil society. He was determined to give women their proper place in society and wanted to enable them to play a leading role in the developmental process of society. While Sati has abolished permanently in 1830, women continue to be harassed and exploited in different forms even today in India. Perhaps they are not physically forced to burn themselves in this husband's funeral pyre, but social evils like dowry deaths, domestic violence, rape, molestation, harassment at the workplace, eve teasing, female infanticide and other formats of subjugating and exploiting women continue unabated, to the extent that so many helpless women contemplate suicide. The reservation of women is not sufficient as the problem is more deep seated and requires transformation of social attitudes towards women and gender in general. In this present context ideas and strategies applied by Roy to empower women in all aspects of society are seem very relevant and significant in present day India where victimization and persecution of women still persist.